

PROSPECTS FOR USE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN COMMERCIAL BANKS

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Abstract. In this article, the principles of digitalization of commercial banks and the use of information and communication technologies of the digital economy, their impact on the quality of service, and the legal basis of digitalization of the banking system in the Republic of Uzbekistan are presented. The article mentions the opinions of foreign and domestic scientists, as well as the foreign experiences of the wide use of digital technologies in improving the quality of service of thiorate banks. At the same time, proposals and conclusions on further improvement of remote service and digitization in commercial banks were formed.

Key words: digital economy, competition, digital transformation, innovation, digital platform, banking services, remote technologies, mobile application.

1. Introduction.

While the times are rapidly developing, the effective use of digital technologies in the financial sectors, as well as the improvement of mechanisms for the large-scale use of remote services in commercial banks, are becoming one of the important quality indicators. Therefore, the principles of digitalization of commercial banks and their impact on the quality of service, as well as the process of digitalization will allow banks to provide services more efficiently and quickly, create convenience for customers and not only reduce operational costs, but also improve digital services, remote banking services and customer relations. makes it possible to improve mutual relations. In this regard, on May 12, 2020, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5992 "On the strategy of reforming the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2025 [1]" came into force , according to which, strengthening of state participation in underserved and vulnerable groups and implementation of targeted measures, wide introduction of remote services for the population and small businesses, development of a network of low-cost service points, as well as the republic as a mutually complementary part of the unified financial system, several tasks were set, such as increasing the popularity and quality of financial services by creating

favorable conditions for the formation and development of non-bank credit organizations. Also, according to the Decree No. PF-6079 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on October 5, 2020, on the approval of the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy and measures for its effective implementation [2], by January 1, 2022, the digital transformation of commercial banks will be completed by providing a wide range of online services, including remote loan products, deposits and account opening. This, in turn, analyzes the impact of Digitization on service quality, including indicators of customer satisfaction, service speed and transparency. It also creates new digital banking trends, risks and strategies to manage them. In general, digitization plays an important role in increasing the competitiveness of commercial banks.

2. Literature review.

In the course of the development of information technology in the world, the term digital economy appeared, and this term was first used in the book "Electronic Digital Society: Advantages and Disadvantages of the Network Age" in 1995. According to Don Tapscott [3], the development of digital culture is considered the main factor of digital transformation of market entities.

The term "digital economy" was put into practice by the American programmer Nicholas Negroponte [4]. Currently, politicians, economists, journalists, businessmen - almost all of them - use this term. In 2016, the World Bank published its first report on the state of the digital economy in the world.

The term "Digital Economy" was introduced into scientific practice by Manuel Castells [5], a Spanish and American sociologist, a leading researcher of the information society. In this regard, he published his three-volume monograph "Information Age: Economy, Society and Culture". According to him, the term digital economy represents two different types of concepts:

First of all, the digital economy is considered a modern stage of development, characterized by the priority of creative work and information benefits.

secondly, the digital economy is a unique theory, the object of its study is the information society. The theory of digital economy is in the initial period of its development, because the transition of civilization to the digital information stage began several decades ago. The factor connecting these concepts is the primary place of information technologies in the globalization of economic processes. In our opinion, the digital economy is not a separate type of activity. In fact, it means business, industrial facilities, services. The term "digital" refers to the active use of information technologies in all these areas. If in the ordinary economy material goods are considered the main resource, in the digital economy it will be

information and data that can be processed and transmitted. After their analysis, a proper management solution is developed.

3. Research methodology.

In this article, economic research methods such as graphical grouping, economic-statistical analysis and synthesis, logical thinking are widely used as research methodology.

4. Analysis and discussion of results.

The provision of remote banking services is a set of services that provide the opportunity to perform various banking operations remotely. It is enough to use a computer or mobile phone without visiting a bank. Also, remote technologies allow the customer to use banking services with maximum convenience and to minimize time and financial costs in the process of working with the bank, and the remote service system can be divided into two types according to the nature of the services provided to customers:

- informative;
- transaction.

Informational banking is focused on providing financial information to customers, while transactional banking provides an opportunity to carry out financial transactions. At the same time, the main principle of remote banking services is the remote exchange of various information between the client and the bank. The bank ensures the security of this operation.

Bank-Client is a computer-based system in which a special program is installed on the client's computer. This program stores all customer information (mainly payment documents and account statements) on the computer. A direct connection between the bank and the client's computer is made through a modem.

Internet banking is a system that allows clients to manage their deposit accounts, including bank card accounts, via the Internet. This type of service is a system designed for making payments in real time while the client is connected to the bank remotely. The user accesses the system through a web browser. The Internet banking system is hosted on the bank's web server. The user has the opportunity to review all his information (payment documents and statements from accounts) on the bank's website, and through the Internet banking service, the client can use it at his place of work or at another location. conveniently:

- transfer payments;
- monitoring the stages of payment;
- makes it possible to use its practices like getting all reports at any time.

Through Internet banking, the client can connect to the bank's website from his workplace, see the money coming into his account and prepare money transfers and send them to the bank.

SMS-banking is a system of receiving information in the form of SMS to bank customers about transactions in their deposit accounts and accounts opened for bank cards. In order to receive information from the account, the client needs to send an SMS request to the bank's special phone number.

Today, residents can perform real-time card-to-card (P2P) money transfer operations, make tax, budget, utility and other payments, receive microloans and repay loans, make online deposits, deposit and widely uses remote opening of loan (credit) accounts, making payments from an international bank card account, online conversion operations and other remote banking services.

On the other hand, for enterprises and organizations, through remote management systems of bank accounts, in real-time, to dispose of funds in bank accounts and make payments, to send an order to the service bank in electronic form for the purchase (conversion) of foreign currency funds. opportunities for sending, transferring monthly salary and equivalent payments to the bank and using other services have been created.

Fig. 1. The number of users of systems providing remote banking services as of October 1, 2024 [6]

In general, the development of banking business activities on the basis of digitization requires the use of innovative approaches in the financial sector and increased experience in providing better services to customers. Through these ways, commercial banks can increase labor productivity, provide competitive advantage in the market of banking services, which in turn will increase the development of the sector and increase income. Digital technologies allow

commercial banks to improve efficiency and security, as well as provide superior customer service and remain competitive in a rapidly changing environment. At the heart of the success of digital transformation in commercial banks is a customer-centric approach. By leveraging digital technologies, banks can better understand and anticipate customer needs and develop long-term relationships. Digital transformation allows commercial banks to innovate and quickly adapt to changing market dynamics.

Today, one of the issues actively studied by the world's leading banks is the creation of a Super-app (collection of functions necessary for the client in a single interface). The cases of recording this issue in annual reports and business plans increased by 640 percent during 2019-2021. The main problem in this direction is related to customer demand. Banking applications have a complex structure, but in most cases customers only use functions such as checking balances, making payments and payment history. Therefore, 4-5 APIs are used to integrate mobile applications with other platforms.

By embracing new technologies and fostering a culture of innovation, banks can differentiate themselves from their competitors, drive growth, and take advantage of new opportunities in the digital ecosystem. Partnerships and strategic partnerships with fintech startups will further accelerate innovation and expand the range of products and services offered to customers. Despite the benefits of digital transformation, banks must prioritize security and compliance to reduce risk and build customer trust.

5. Conclusions and suggestions.

Therefore, the digital transformation of financial services will create a wide range of opportunities for bank customers, and will help to expand the economic opportunities of customers, while being considered an important stage for increasing financial activity. That is, one of the prospects of digital banks is that the cost of services will be reduced by 40-60 percent due to digitalization of financial networks. It allows customers to save money and time spent on visiting the bank and preparing documents.

In a word, the transformation process of commercial banks and the change to work in the digital banking system is a response to the development and active spread of new information technologies around the world, and digital technologies not only increase the quality of products and services, but also reduce excess costs. In other words, the development of digital financial services is an important direction for the development of the country's banking and financial system.

The above figures indicate that the quality services offered by the bank based on the principle of rapid development and customer orientation are widely

accepted by customers, and the number of bank customers is increasing day by day. This indicates that a new digital banking trend has begun in the banking and financial system of our country. For this reason, it is becoming a requirement of time for traditional banks to pay great attention to the development of digital banking services.

6. List of used literature:

1. Decree No. PF-5992 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 12, 2020 "On the strategy of reforming the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2025".

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